

Atmospheric Iodine and Fluctuations of SARS-Cov-2 Prevalence in Iran, Germany, Turkey and France

Mohammad Reza Besharati, PhD Candidate, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran
Nafiseh Jafari, Graduate Student, Malek Ashtar University of Technology, Tehran, Iran
Dr. Mohammad Izadi, Associate Professor, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran
Dr. Alireza Talebpour, Associate Professor, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran

Dear Editor,

1- According to the results of lifestyle and SARS-Cov-2 research [1][2], the concentration of iodine in the body has an important effect on SARS-Cov-2 risks.

2. In the atmosphere, there are aerosols containing ocean iodine [3]. This iodine in the air rises from the oceans and moves through the earth's wind cycle.

3- The prevailing direction of the wind in the middle latitudes of the northern hemisphere is from the Atlantic coast to Europe, then Turkey and then Iran [4].

4. Some increases in the SARS-Cov-2 peak in Iran, France, Turkey and Germany have been simultaneous, with a few delays, after by after.

5. The recent SARS-Cov-2 peak (3 April 2021) began in the west of the country (Iran) and slowly came a little to the east. The east of the country is not involved yet. The prevailing direction of the wind is from west to east.

6- As the air warms, the entry of iodine from the ocean into the atmosphere increases many times over [5].

This evidences suggest that the current SARS-Cov-2 peak in Iran and recent peaks in Turkey, Germany, and France have a common climatic cause, which is that the summer ocean iodine wave enters the atmosphere and travels from west to east with atmospheric winds. And God knows. Thanks and courtesy.

Figure 1- COVID-19 State in Iran, 3 April 2021.

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